

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

Collaboration plan with definition of
common objectives and activities,
including milestones

Deliverable D7.5

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.5

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

The present deliverable describes synergies and collaboration with the CSA CASTIEL 2 (Grant No 101102047) and the other Centers of Excellence (CoE) complementary to ESiWACE3.

The activities include identifying common objectives, defining and implementing a collaboration plan, and defining related project-specific milestones. This collaboration plan will be updated whenever significant changes arise, at least in months 17, 35, and 47.

The ESiWACE3 CoE follows two paths of collaborating with the EuroHPC landscape: A common, coordinated one, which is described in detail in *CASTIEL 2 Deliverable 1.7 - Collaboration Plan with the CoEs*, and an individual one, which is described in this document.

2. Conclusion & Results

The "Collaboration Plan" is described in section 4. It is the starting point for establishing a first communication and implementing the collaboration strategy with CASTIEL 2, the host entities, the NCCs and other CoEs. It sets out the statement of intent that will be changed and adapted as necessary as the project evolves, following the guidelines of CASTIEL 2. Updates to this plan are foreseen in the progress reports (months 17, 35 and 47).

No results have been obtained so far. They are expected in about a year.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
A1: Transfer and establish knowledge and technology	Yes
A2: Close common technology gaps	
A3: Serve as a sustainable community hub	Yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
O4: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services	Yes
O5: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	Yes
O6: Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth System modelling across Earth System science and HPC and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1. Collaboration with CASTIEL 2

The collaboration with CASTIEL 2 CSA is detailed in the corresponding deliverable of this CSA. The following subsections provide a summary.

4.1.1. Legacy Codes

Legacy Codes are software packages with a long lifetime of prior development. The majority of the big climate and weather models fall into this category. They tend to have large code bases written in Fortran and have evolved over decades.

Many of these codes require software re-engineering to facilitate or, in many cases, even enable migration and maintenance on JU systems (both current and future). One central work package of ESiWACE3 provides software engineering services to help code developers from the weather and climate community in this effort, e.g. by porting codes to GPUs. ESiWACE3 is, therefore, well placed to help explain and identify re-engineering requirements for legacy codes in terms of personnel resources and time scales and to provide suggestions for actions to meet those requirements.

We would like to emphasise that it is beyond the scope of a single CoEs to solve this problem. It needs a collaborative effort of code owners, software experts (in the case of the services offered by ESiWACE from a CoE), manufacturers (eg with respect to compiler support), and hosting sites.

4.1.2. CI/CD Platform

The objective is to ease the deployment and support from CASTIEL to ESiWACE3 applications onto some of the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC) supercomputers. To lower this hurdle and enable ESiWACE3 code owners and end users to deploy applications with minimal overhead on multiple supercomputers, CASTIEL 2 coordinates the implementation of a common continuous integration and deployment platform across all EuroHPC supercomputers. In the first phase, CoEs such as ESiWACE3 can conveniently deploy their codes on several EuroHPC supercomputers, ideally with minimal or no code changes. Such a CI/CD platform also allows for automatic testing and code quality checks that will help improve the maturity of the ESiWACE3 codes.

To foster the implementation of such an integration platform, CASTIEL 2 coordinates this activity while bringing together representatives from some current and future EuroHPC supercomputing sites. CASTIEL 2 has set up a mailing list early on to facilitate discussions between all stakeholders and organises monthly conference calls to guide the integration process and provide an open space for discussion.

4.1.3. Special access scheme

CASTIEL 2 will support the CoEs as ESiWACE3 in achieving appropriate resource access to the EuroHPC supercomputers to enable us to reach our objectives for deploying and delivering efficient, highly-performant application software on the systems required for our users. For this purpose, CASTIEL 2 prepared several surveys to gather initial requirements for access to and use of the EuroHPC supercomputers (for development, benchmarking and performance optimisation) from all CoEs, including ESiWACE3. Based on a thorough analysis of the survey data, CASTIEL 2 compiled a detailed proposal submitted in project month 3 to the EuroHPC JU to justify a special access scheme specifically for the CoEs as a strategic part of the EuroHPC JU's programme.

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The input provided by the CoEs has unveiled their plans to deploy about 60 different codes and pilots to the EuroHPC supercomputers. ESiWACE3 participated, including our codes' application for weather and climate and our preferences for access to some of the EuroHPC platforms. In general, their requests align with the allocated computer resource limits of the individual EuroHPC JU systems. However, the overall input reveals significant uncertainty regarding the required computing resources and their compatibility with different systems. To ensure the timely initiation of the CoE activities on the EuroHPC JU systems, CASTIEL 2 proposed two initial access models:

1. A "flat-rate" or "base-rate" approach for benchmark and development-type access. This approach assigns a fixed amount of resources to each code, enabling quick access to gather the necessary technical experience and conduct benchmarking runs on different machines. It includes access to all systems for benchmarking purposes and selected systems for development.
2. An individualised yet accelerated approach for regular and high-priority access.

ESiWACE3 will work with CASTIEL 2, following the progress of the special access for our users.

4.1.4. Supporting activities

Collaboration between CoEs and NCCs

This mechanism is situated in CASTIEL 2 WP2, which is responsible for facilitating networking & collaboration across National Competence Centers (NCCs) and CoEs and fostering NCC/CoE collaboration. The first step is to support the operation of a communication channel between all CoEs (the HPC CoE Council) ESiWACE3 was invited to join this channel, and we are following their communications. These communication channels will then facilitate regular discussions between NCCs and CoEs on topics of mutual interest to enable initiatives and working groups.

In parallel, CASTIEL 2 WP2 will define and run workshops on non-technical, relevant topics and competences (soft skills, complementary competencies) based on the needs expressed by NCCs and CoEs—and make the materials available. Topics will either be sourced from the NCC/CoE discussions or from the knowledge CASTIEL 2 has from its management perspective.

4.1.5. CoE contribution to CASTIEL 2 objectives

Training Framework

This task aims to facilitate access to training offered at the national and European levels to interested NCCs and other potential users (from industry, academia or the public sector). This includes improved coordination and increased availability of training activities on HPC across NCCs, CoEs and within the European HPC ecosystem through the centralised training portal of training opportunities in Europe.

This task will also establish effective cooperation and leverage synergies with other European initiatives in the area of training in HPC, including [EUMaster4HPC](#) and [ETP4HPC](#), among others. A common certification baseline of training and modular training approaches will also be addressed. This task will therefore establish a task force inviting, on the one hand, NCCs, CoEs as ESiWACE3, and the previously mentioned European initiatives, and on the other hand, certification experts such as the HPC Certification Forum and European certification agencies to jointly map out the situation and work on the training framework (which then is handed over to the CoEs and NCCs for prototypical implementation). Moreover, this task will coordinate defining and implementing the European HPC training baseline for industry, SMEs, academia/research/the public sector.

ESiWACE3 WP5 has a membership in the CASTIEL 2-coordinated task force for training materials.

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C2ISS

CASTIEL2 starts with a set of websites (www.euroccaccess.eu, www.hpccoe.eu), which must be integrated into one unified platform solution. The new Web platform (working title: C2ISS) will not only include information about training offers but also about actors from the HPC system, their services & offerings and more. Figure 1 shows an overview of the individual components and services the portal will support.

Figure 1: Overview of C2ISS.

ESiWACE3 and other CoEs will participate in periodic meetings coordinated by CASTIEL2 to ensure that ESiWACE3's needs are met with the new Web platform. ESiWACE3 will be integrated into all steps of the iterative design process of the C2ISS.

4.2. Collaboration with Hosting Entities

Centers hosting the EuroHPC JU machines:

- **BSC, CSC, and JSC** are also ESiWACE3 partners. We will, in particular, implement our HPCW benchmark on those machines.
 - BSC, CSC and JSC will support the deployment of HPCW and climate and weather applications on MN5 and LUMI, providing guidance to ensure that the different applications are taking advantage of the CPU and GPU partitions efficiently.
- We expect that the contact with **other hosting** sites will be facilitated by CASTIEL 2, and we aim at porting HPCW to several sites providing those sites show interest and will provide the necessary support.
- We will also encourage the experts at other hosting sites (and other organisations involved in CASTIEL 2) to send their experts to support ESiWACE3 training events (and vice versa) to facilitate networking and knowledge transfer.
 - We have already been interested in collaborating on the 1st ESiWACE3 Hackathon, "[Running weather and climate models on LUMI](#)".

4.3. Complementary Centers of Excellence (CoEs)

The ESiWACE3 project has selected the following CoEs whose activities are complementary and with whom potential synergies would be more effective.

It is interesting to note that most of the CoEs should have some co-design activities (hardware, software, codes), including the collaboration with HPC vendors and the identification of suitable applications relevant to the development of European HPC technologies towards exascale and collaboration with European initiatives (e.g. EPI, RISC- V, EuroHPC JU Pilots). Thus, co-design is a common topic that can certainly lead to close collaborations with all CoEs. Table 1 shows the main CoEs of interest for ESiWACE3.

Table 1. Centers of Excellence of main interest for ESiWACE3.

CoE acronym and title	Coordinator	Summary	ESiWACE3 partners involved
CHEESE 2P - Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Exascale in Solid Earth Phase 2	Geosciences Barcelona (GEO3BCN – CSIC)	ChEESE is the Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Exascale in Solid Earth. It aims to become a hub for HPC software within the solid earth community. ChEESE aims to address the challenges posed by geohazards and accurate predictions with the help of exascale computers.	BSC, Atos
eflows4HPC - Centre of Excellence (CoE) for workflows in HPC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)	eflows4HPC is a workflow platform integrating methodologies to widen the access to HPC to selected user communities. It aims to design complex applications in integrating HPC processes, data analytics, and AI.	BSC, CSC, CMCC, Atos
BioExcel-3 - Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Computational Biomolecular Research	KTH Royal Institute of Technology (KTH)	BioExcel-3 provides open-source molecular modelling and simulation software, applications, tools, user support, and community-building events for Life Scientists. This will enable Life Scientists to address grand scientific challenges by fully exploiting the power of data and computing e-infrastructure.	BSC, CSC
MaX - Materials Design at the Exascale	Istituto Nanoscienze - Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)	MaX is the Centre of Excellence (CoE) for the MAterials design at the eXascale. This CoE aims to upscale the MaX codes and their performance to multiple heterogeneous exascale architectures, endow these codes with innovative capabilities enabled by such architectures and co-design the hardware and software in collaboration with the relevant European stakeholders.	Atos, BSC, Julich
HiDALGO2 - HPC and Big Data Technologies for Global Challenges	Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC)	HiDALGO2's mission is to provide effective and accurate simulations covering global challenges. The information will be provided quickly, considering changing weather and traffic conditions.	Atos

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A number of concrete activities have already been identified or planned for potential collaboration for the months until the first update of this document (month 17). Table 2 summarises these initial actions planned to collaborate effectively with complementary CoEs. This table is only a first approach; it will be updated as the project progresses. We expect that the identification of further areas of cooperation between CoEs will be facilitated by activities coordinated by CASTIEL 2.

Table 2. Actions planned to collaborate effectively with complementary CoEs.

Collaboration activity	Title/Description	CoEs involved	Expected date	Venue (face-to-face/virtual)
Regular meetings to synchronise research and development activities	HANAMI	Within the framework of the HANAMI project, targeting a closer collaboration in the field of HPC between the EU and Japan, common activities between ESiWACE3 partners (in particular BSC, DKRZ, ECMWF), BioEXcel, and MaX also involving EuroHPC JU hosting sites, will be addressed.	Starting October 2023	Collaboration within a project
Benchmarking exercises	Exchanging feedback on benchmark activities toward preparing the applications for European technologies	Potentially all	To be defined	Virtual/Face-to-face. Depending on the format of the existing initiatives.
Best practices	Investigate the possibility of leveraging existing educational initiatives to introduce the concept of CoEs and simulation to high school students. The objective is threefold: outreach, education, and promoting female profiles in computing. After this pilot, we would explore the possibility of creating additional educational materials (D6.1).	ESiWACE3, MAX	Mid 2024	Virtual/Face-to-face. Depending on the format of the existing initiatives.
Joint publication and dissemination of results	To be defined	Potentially all. We expect that this will be addressed in the general assembly of CoEs organised by CASTIEL2 (under the lead of CASTIEL2 WP3). In addition, we will discuss dissemination and publication during the specific co-operations with individual CoEs (D6.1).	-	-
Joint events: workshops, hackathons, etc.	HPC workflows for climate models workshop (D6.1)	eflows4HPC and Climateurope2	17 October 2023	CSC premises

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Collaboration activity	Title/Description	CoEs involved	Expected date	Venue (face-to-face/virtual)
	The first ESiWACE3 Summer School is planned to be a shared event with the WarmWorld project (D6.1)	ESiWACE3	Summer 2024	CSC premises
	CoEs Open Day event	Potentially all CoEs. It will be addressed to high school students to raise their interest in HPC research careers.	First semester of 2024	BSC premises
	Identify an event focused on HPC that we could attend with a unified message promoting the use of simulations and supercomputing. The idea is to bring together our respective CoEs, and perhaps others who might be interested, to construct a shared booth at the event. In addition to the booth, we would promote creating content to be shared coordinately in social networks.	ESiWACE3 and MAX. Potentially other CoEs	Second semester of 2023.	Virtual/Face-to-face. Depending on the international event format.
Common best practices for IP management	To be defined	-	-	-
Concrete measures for identification of common routines/algorithms /modules	To be defined	-	-	-
Creation and extension of software libraries used by multiple codes across disciplines	To be defined	-	-	-

5. References

- CASTIEL2 (GA 101102047) (2023) *Collaboration Plan with the CoEs - Deliverable 1.7.*
- ESiWACE3 D6.1. (2023). *Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan - Deliverable D6.1*
<https://zenodo.org/record/8098830>

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

This deliverable's main difficulty is agreeing on the most feasible activities in joint with other CoEs. This document is a preliminary plan that sets the basis for collaboration in the following years. It will be updated periodically.

7. How does this deliverable contribute to the EuroHPC strategy

This deliverable, by describing potential synergies and collaboration with the CASTIEL 2 and the other Centers of Excellence (CoE) complementary to ESiWACE3, contributes to the EuroHPC strategy to develop the necessary technologies applications, and skills for reaching exascale capabilities and to develop and support a highly competitive and innovative high-performance computing ecosystem.

8. Sustainability

To our understanding, most of the actions addressed in this document and, in fact, the collaboration plan itself are inherent elements of the EuroHPC JU strategy to create a vivid and sustained European HPC community. Specific collaborations like bilateral exchange with some other CoEs will also contribute to the more general CDEP actions of ESiWACE3, which we always see as part of a longer-term community strategy.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

We are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

- Making this document available on the [project website](#)
- Making this document available on the [ESiWACE Zenodo Community](#) (the Open Access repository for scientific results)

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

N/A

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

N/A

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

N/A